

Original Research

Designing a Mixed Method Study in the Field of Green Marketing Strategy: Evidence from Iraq Oil and Gas Industry

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Abstract

This research endeavor was conducted with the objective of discerning and prioritizing the determinants that influence the execution of green marketing strategies by Iraqi executives operating in the oil and gas sector. The research adopted a mix methodology, wherein factors were elicited through thematic analysis in the initial phase and subsequently assessed through AHP in the subsequent phase. At the first part, a comprehensive review of a related scholarly articles published between the years 2018 and 2024 was diligently carried out. The data gleaned from these articles was subsequently analyzed and categorized utilizing the advanced MAXQDA software 18. Consequently, a total of 5 overarching categories of factors that play a pivotal role in influencing the implementation of green marketing strategies were identified: economic and political factors, competitive factors, organizational factors, governmental factors, social awareness, and environmental factors. At the second part, through the utilization of the Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP), a total of 10 engaged Iraqi oil industry executives took part in the prioritization endeavor. The outcomes reveal that economic and political elements wield a paramount influence on the implementation of eco-friendly marketing strategies. This investigation furnishes valuable perspectives for executives and decision-makers within the Iraqi petroleum sector, facilitating a deeper comprehension of the fundamental factors that impact the embrace of eco-friendly marketing strategies and the formulation of efficacious approaches for sustainable advancement.

Keywords: AHP approach, green marketing strategy, Iraqi managers, strategy implementation, thematic analysis.

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Introduction

Green marketing plays a pivotal role in the oil and gas sector for a variety of compelling reasons. Primarily, it enables these organizations to attain a competitive edge and enhance market performance through alignment with global environmental standards and meeting consumer expectations regarding sustainable practices (Al-Murad, 2022; Mashkoor et al., 2023). The implementation of green marketing tactics also has the potential to bolster the industry's public image and brand power, given the growing consumer preference for environmentally friendly products and services (Cheng et al., 2023). Furthermore, the integration of green activity-based costing (GABC) can make a noteworthy contribution to sustainability efforts by mitigating the adverse impacts of industrial waste and enhancing economic efficiency (Mashkoor et al., 2023). Environmental advancements like green logistics and green supply chain management are imperative for generating positive externalities and ensuring the long-term sustainability of the oil and gas domain (Sasu et al., 2017).

The linkage between green marketing, industrial ecology, and environmental sustainability is crucial, as it addresses key issues such as extended producer responsibility and eco-efficiency, which are vital for diminishing the environmental footprint of the oil and gas industry (Asha, 2017). By embracing green marketing practices, companies in the Iraqi oil and gas sector can not only adhere to environmental mandates but also cultivate trust among consumers and stakeholders, thereby securing their viability and prosperity in a market increasingly prioritizing environmental conservation (Al-Hersh, A. M., & Aburoub, 2015).

In this particular viewpoint, the prioritization of factors influencing the execution of green marketing strategy holds significant importance for various reasons. Initially, it assists organizations in the effective allocation of resources and concentration on the most influential areas, ensuring that endeavors are not squandered on less crucial factors (Mammadova et al., 2023). This is especially critical within the realm of sustainability, where the inclusion of green marketing strategies can result in notable competitive advantages by meeting the escalating consumer demand for eco-friendly products and services (López-Torres et al., 2023; Esmaelnezhad et al., 2023). Moreover, giving priority to factors like waste minimization, environmental impact reduction, and consumer engagement can notably enhance the efficacy of green marketing strategies, as these components have been recognized as carrying the highest significance in accomplishing sustainability objectives (Vilkaite-Vaitone & Skackauskiene, 2020). Additionally, comprehending and dealing with both internal and external factors, such as organizational culture, managerial competencies, and external influences, can facilitate the seamless integration of these strategies, thereby diminishing discrepancies and elevating overall organizational effectiveness (Vevere & Shina, 2023). Furthermore, prioritization supports the identification of the most impactful determinants, such as the 6 R concepts (reduce, reuse, recover, recycle, remanufacture, and redesign), which are crucial for green product development and can propel the adoption of green practices in manufacturing (Vardhan et al., 2022). It also empowers marketers to more efficiently target specific consumer segments, especially those with environmental awareness, thereby nurturing heightened consumer allegiance and contentment (Garg et al., 2021). For example, in the tourism

industry, emphasizing innovative advertising technologies and sustainable tourism practices can amplify market outreach and customer contentment (Taghavi et al., 2021). Overall, a methodical approach to prioritizing these factors ensures that green marketing strategies are not solely executed proficiently but also yield the desired environmental and economic advantages. This study aims to address the query of which factors influence the execution of green marketing strategy and what priority they hold according to Iraqi managers.

Literature review

Green marketing, a core marketing concept, gives significant importance to promoting products and practices that are eco-friendly. This involves using sustainable materials, adopting eco-friendly production methods, incorporating green packaging, implementing pricing strategies that consider the environment, establishing sustainable distribution channels, and using environmentally conscious advertising techniques as discussed by Pacevičiūtė & Razbadauskaitė-Venskė (2023). Implementing a green marketing strategy involves fulfilling a company's social responsibility by addressing environmental issues, thus aiding in environmental preservation, economic growth, and sustainable development (Chauhan & Naznin, 2023). This strategic approach allows companies to build a positive brand image, enhance their industry reputation, and meet consumer demands in a competitive market environment (Gupta and Dharwal, 2022). Furthermore, green marketing plays a crucial role in influencing consumer behavior and purchase decisions, especially as individuals become more aware of the environmental impacts of products (Chang et al., 2019). The COVID-19 pandemic has emphasized the importance of green marketing, with consumers increasingly preferring sustainable products (Manunggal, 2022). Engaging in green marketing activities, like promoting eco-friendly products and utilizing social media for marketing, can expand market reach and appeal to a wider consumer base.

Green marketing, also known as sustainable or environmental marketing, is a key concept in modern trade practices, integrating environmental considerations into product innovation, development, distribution strategies, and consumer engagement (Kotler et al., 2010). The main goal of green marketing is to endorse products and services that have minimal negative environmental impacts, promoting sustainability and eco-consciousness in line with Peattie's insights (2016).

In the contemporary era, an increasing number of individuals are shifting their focus towards green marketing as they recognize the crucial importance of taking proactive steps to tackle the escalating environmental challenges, particularly those arising from climate change. The impacts of climate change are evident in the rising temperatures of the Earth, worsened by the overexploitation of resources, widespread pollution, and the alarming loss of natural habitats. These urgent issues have led both businesses and consumers to rethink their roles and duties in protecting the environment, leading to a shift in their attitudes and actions towards environmental conservation (Wymer & Polonsky, 2015).

Green marketing goes beyond environmental stewardship; it extends into the strategic and financial domains of companies, highlighting its multifaceted importance in today's

business environments. As environmental awareness grows among individuals connected to polluting industries, a noticeable trend is emerging where they are increasingly favoring products and brands that promote eco-friendliness and sustainability. This changing consumer preference offers companies a chance to boost their competitiveness by adjusting their marketing strategies and pollution control efforts to align with the desires of environmentally conscious consumers (Mukonza et al., 2021). Furthermore, businesses that embrace green marketing principles and implement eco-friendly production methods often find themselves in a favorable position in terms of meeting evolving environmental laws and requirements. Through adopting environmentally sustainable practices and promoting sustainable products, companies can reduce risks, strengthen their resilience, and ensure compliance with regulatory frameworks, thus enhancing their ability to adapt to legal changes and minimize potential disruptions (Firdiansyah et al., 2021).

Methodology

The current research is a mixed-method study based on the principles of pragmatism paradigm. In this study, factors were elicited through thematic analysis in the initial phase and subsequently ranked through AHP in the subsequent phase. At the first part, a comprehensive review of related scholarly articles published between the years 2018 and 2024 was diligently carried out. The data gleaned from these articles was subsequently analyzed and categorized utilizing the advanced MAXQDA software 18. Consequently, a total of 5 overarching categories of factors that play a pivotal role in influencing the implementation of green marketing strategies were identified. At the second part, through the utilization of the Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP), a total of 10 engaged Iraqi oil industry executives took part in the prioritization endeavor.

Phase 1: Qualitative part

In this step, a thematic analysis is conducted. The process of coding is shown as follow:

Initial Coding: Prominent statements and phrases concerning factors impacting green marketing strategy implementation were pinpointed and encoded.

Searching for Themes: The primary codes underwent scrutiny, and interconnected codes were clustered together to establish potential sub-themes.

Reviewing Themes: The sub-themes underwent evaluation and enhancement to guarantee their accurate representation of the data and their distinctiveness from one another.

Defining and Naming Themes: The sub-themes were further scrutinized, leading to the identification and naming of 5 principal theme categories based on data patterns observed.

Credibility Assessment: The research findings' credibility was evaluated using the criteria outlined by Guba and Lincoln (1994), encompassing credibility, transferability, dependability, and confirmability.

By employing this thematic analysis methodology, the study successfully identified and classified the pivotal factors influencing the integration of green marketing strategies through a comprehensive review of related articles.

In accordance with Guba and Lincoln (1994), the data were validated to ascertain the reliability and validity of the outcomes. Initially, in order to ensure the researcher's depiction and interpretation accurately mirrors reality, the extracted codes were distributed to various marketing experts to gauge the accuracy of the coding. Qualitative data analysis, formulated meanings, and outcomes were examined by five qualitative analysis experts. To ascertain the consistency in data collection auditability and study result inference, this research utilized Colaizzi's (1978) seven-step analysis process. Furthermore, expert insights were sought to elucidate themes and thematic clusters in the study findings (Morrow et al., 2015). Ultimately, to mitigate bias, uphold impartiality in both the process and outcomes of the study, and thereby ensure verifiability, the researcher endeavored to grasp the qualitative data presented in the articles realistically.

After extracting primary and secondary codes, secondary and main themes were obtained in the next step. 5 Categories of Factors Affecting the Implementation of Green Marketing Strategy:

Table 1. The main factors affecting green marketing strategy implementation

Sources	Sub themes	Main themes
Amin et al., (2020) Faraz et al. (2024)	Importance of community awareness about the necessity of using green products	Social and Environmental Awareness
Panait et al., (2023) Elsaman & Sergio, (2021) Dementieva & Sokolova, (2022) Duttagupta et al., (2021) Alshabebi, H. (2020). Tuni et al., (2020) Javeed et al., (2022) Umar and Wei, (2022)	Increase in environmental awareness within society	
Ibrahim et al., (2020) Aswad et al., (2023) Adamo et al., (2018) Johnston & Cushing (2020)	Media's growing focus on environmental crises	
Khan et al., (2021) Rizvi, Y. S., & Garg, R. (2021) Aastvedt et al., (2021)	Rising demand from people for environmental protection	

Shah et al., (2022) Saeed et al., (2023) Kadhim et al., (2020) Koshesh & Jafari, (2019) Heim et al., (2023) Ahmad & Satrovic, (2023)	Government laws and regulations	Governmental Factors
Wang & Pan, (2023) Lin & Lin,)2023) Zheng & Duan, (2023)	Importance of government support	
Ben-Naceur, (2019) Tillotson et al., (2023)	Availability of sufficient financial resources for environmental preservation	
Jianling Xu et al., (2023) Chen and Wang, (2022) Zhao et al., (2022)	Importance of government infrastructures	
Obeidat et al., (2020) Oluwasanmi & Ogunro, (2018) Aastvedt et al., (2021)	Importance of evaluating companies' performance based on green criteria	Organizational Factors
Kaupke & zu Knyphausen-Aufseß, (2023) Mansour et al., (2020)	Increased costs and production expenses with green marketing strategies	
Bratanegara et al., (2022) Rademaker and Royne (2018)	Lack of interest and awareness among managers	
Vilkaite-Vaitone & Skackauskiene, (2020) Alzghoul et al., (2024)	Complexity of implementing green marketing strategies	
Resen & AbdulRazzaq, (2022) Ali, (2023)	Importance of achieving environmental standards	
Aleksandrov et al., (2022)	Importance of developing clean technologies	Competitive and Business Factors
Aswad et al., (2023) Mäkitie et al., (2019) Saeed et al., (2023) Pacevičiūtė and Razbadauskaitė-Venskė (2023) Barforoush et al., (2021)	Necessity to stay competitive	

Motilewa et al., (2019)	Channel for socially conscious consumer communication	
Al-Waeli et al., (2020) Ben-Naceur, (2019) Tillotson et al., (2023)	Need to expand collaboration with other countries on environmental issues	
Al Mashkoor, (2022) Lai et al., (2023) Guo et al., (2020) Mojarad et al., (2018)	Requirement for developing future-oriented business models	
Wang & Ozturk, (2023) Cismaş et al., (2023)	Priority of sustainable management practices in the global green chain	
Ibrahim et al., (2020) Aswad et al., (2023) Adamo et al., (2018) Johnston & Cushing (2020)	Seriousness of environmental crises	Economic and Political Factors
Azam et al., (2023) Bond et al., (2018) Ahmad & Satrovic, (2023)	Political prioritization of the environment	
Marsiglio & Privileggi, (2021)	Uneven relationship between environmental protection and economic growth/employment	

Source: (yousif et al., 2024)

Phase 2: Quantitative part

The Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) is a technique utilized for the arrangement and examination of intricate decisions using mathematical and psychological principles. Originating in the 1970s by Thomas L. Saaty, this method has undergone subsequent enhancements. Divided into three components, it encompasses the main objective or issue to be resolved, the various potential solutions known as alternatives, and the standards utilized to assess these alternatives. AHP offers a coherent structure for making necessary decisions by quantifying both the criteria and alternatives, and establishing connections between these elements and the overarching goal. Stakeholders have the ability to assess the significance of criteria through pairwise comparisons at any given moment. AHP transforms these assessments into numerical values that can be contrasted with all feasible criteria, distinguishing it from other decision-making methodologies. In the concluding phase of the process, numerical priorities are determined for each alternative. These numerical values signify the most advantageous solutions, reflecting the preferences of all involved stakeholders.

The steps or stages of problem formation and its solution by AHP are examined below.

Step 1: Different Options or Responses the AHP process begins by defining the options to be evaluated

Step 2: Defining the problem and criteria

Step 3: Mutual or pairwise comparison of priorities

Step 4: Compatibility check

Step 5: Calculation of relative weights

In the qualitative part or in the first phase of this research, steps 1 and 2 were practically completed and the options and criteria that should be compared were identified in that phase. These factors are: Economic and Political Factors, Competitive and Business Factors, Organizational Factors, Governmental Factors, Social and Environmental Awareness.

Step 3: Mutual or pairwise comparison of priorities

The second level of the hierarchy consists of the main criteria. First, the weight of each of the main criteria is determined by pairwise comparison of the main criteria based on the goal. Therefore, we have to compare the criteria based on the goal two by two.

Table 2. Pairwise comparison table of factors affecting green marketing strategy implementation in Iraq

	Organizational Factors		Governmental Factors		Social and Environmental		Economic and Political Factors		Competitive and Business Factors	
Organizational Factors	1	1								
Governmental Factors	7	5	1	1						
Social and Environmental Awareness	2	5	2	6	1	1				
Economic and Political Factors	9	7	8	5	9	2	1	1		
Competitive and Business Factors	9	8	7	8	5	9	5	7	1	1

Step 4: Compatibility check

The basis of the calculations of the hierarchical analysis process is based on the primary judgment of the decision maker, which appears in the form of a matrix of paired comparisons. Therefore, any error and inconsistency in the comparison of elements affects the final result obtained from the calculations. The inconsistency ratio is an indicator that shows how much the pairwise comparisons are consistent with each other. Pairwise comparisons are made by experts and the results of the comparisons can be trusted if these comparisons are consistent.

Table 3. The weight obtained from the comparison of criteria

	Organizational Factors	Governmental Factors	Social and Environmental Awareness	Competitive and Business Factors	Organizational Factors	Weight
Organizational Factors	0/19191	0/158	0/216	0/238	0/143	0/18934
Governmental Factors	0/26868	0/221	0/26	0/17	0/183	0/22054
Social and Environmental Awareness	0/07676	0/074	0/087	0/068	0/289	0/118762
Economic and Political Factors	0/24674	0/354	0/389	0/306	0/225	0/304085
Competitive and Business Factors	0/2159	0/193	0/048	0/218	0/16	0/167273

Table 4. The Consistency Index of Indicators

The indicator	Weight	Priority
Organizational Factors	0/189	3
Governmental Factors	0/221	2
Social and Environmental Awareness	0/119	5
Economic and Political Factors	0/304	1
Competitive and Business Factors	0/167	4
CI=	0/098	
n=	5	

The inconsistency ratio serves as an indicator of the degree to which the pairwise comparisons align with one another. These comparisons are conducted by experts and the reliability of their outcomes depends on the consistency between them. When the consistency ratio falls below 0.1, the comparisons are deemed acceptable. Conversely, if the ratio exceeds this threshold, a reassessment of the comparisons is warranted. In this case, the consistency index CI is calculated at 0/098, thus meeting the acceptable criterion.

Discussion

Based on data analysis in the qualitative part of this research, 5 main factors affect the implementation of green marketing strategy. These factors include economic and political factors, government factors, organization-related factors, competitive and business-related factors, and finally social and environmental factors. In order to see how effective these factors are according to Iraqi managers, they were prioritized them using the AHP method. The interesting result that was obtained was that according to Iraqi managers, political and economic factors have the highest effect and social and environmental factors have the least effect in the implementation of green marketing strategy. This result is in line to what Vihristyuk and Dimitrova (2022), asserted in their study. According to them, political and economic factors significantly influence the adoption of green

marketing strategies in the oil and gas industry, often more than social and environmental factors. Political communication can create competitive advantages and help firms navigate environmental regulations, thereby enhancing environmental and financial performance.

Economic and Political Factors encompasses diverse components, such as the gravity of ecological emergencies, governmental focus on environmental issues, and the intricate interconnection between environmental preservation and economic advancement / employment. The gravity of ecological crises presents a notable obstacle with far-reaching consequences for both enterprises and the community. Given the escalating severity of global warming, pollution, and resource exhaustion, there is an escalating necessity for enterprises to adopt sustainable methodologies and promote environmentally sustainable goods. Nonetheless, the political spotlight on environmental concerns fluctuates, with specific administrations prioritizing economic development and expansion over environmental conservation.

Consistent with the outcomes of this inquiry, there exist additional investigations in the academic literature. For instance, Shittu, O., & Nygaard (2021) contend that Economic and social consciousness significantly impact the execution of environmentally friendly marketing tactics by molding consumer behavior and corporate procedures. Social consciousness, particularly concerning ecological sustainability, nurtures green trust and benevolence, which can stimulate impulsive purchases of eco-friendly products at premium costs, thereby reinforcing firms' sustainability commitments and disclosure objectives.

This awareness also encourages consumers to support businesses that demonstrate corporate social responsibility (CSR) and green marketing initiatives, as seen in the positive impact on purchase intentions when companies actively promote their eco-friendly efforts (Khalil & khalil, 2022). Moreover, the integration of green marketing into corporate strategies and CSR programs not only builds a positive green image but also benefits the community and public health, as evidenced by Unilever's successful initiatives in Jakarta (Widyastuti et al., 2019). However, the effectiveness of these strategies can vary across cultures, with a notable value-action gap in rapidly growing Asian economies like Malaysia, where consumers' environmental concerns do not always translate into purchasing behavior (Ottman et al., 2006)

At the other hand, Governmental factors are in the second place. These factors play a pivotal role in shaping the implementation of green marketing strategies, as evidenced by scholarly research. This category encompasses government laws and regulations, governmental support, financial resources allocated for environmental conservation, and government infrastructures. The influence of government laws and regulations is profound in molding the business landscape for green marketing, establishing directives for environmental safeguarding and fostering fair competition. Governmental support, which includes tax benefits and financial aid, is crucial in incentivizing businesses to engage in sustainable practices, while the provision of financial resources for environmental preservation helps promote green initiatives. Moreover, government infrastructures like waste management systems and eco-friendly transportation networks are indispensable for facilitating green marketing efforts through the provision of

essential resources and facilities for efficient execution. Aligning with these findings, Cheng et al. (2022) emphasize the significant role of Governmental factors in shaping the adoption of green marketing strategies. Research indicates that government initiatives such as subsidies and tax policies can greatly impact the competitiveness and profitability of green supply chains (GSCs). Additionally, government interventions can discourage opportunistic behaviors in green supply chain management (GSCM) by incentivizing firms to embrace eco-friendly practices and contribute to the development of a sustainable green product market (Fenglan, 2010). Furthermore, government support, including funding for research and development (R&D) and sales incentives, influences companies' decisions in producing environmentally sustainable goods, consequently leading to varied impacts on environmental outcomes and highlighting the intricate interplay between government policies and environmental consequences (Cohen et al., 2019).

Organizational factors are the third category of factors based on priority. The investigation accentuates the significance of organizational elements in impacting the execution of eco-friendly marketing tactics. Essential components within this classification involve the assessment of firms' achievements based on environmentally friendly standards, heightened expenses and manufacturing costs, disinterest among executives, intricacy of execution, and attaining ecological benchmarks. The assessment of firms' accomplishments based on green standards is pivotal for endorsing eco-friendly marketing methodologies, yet it might also result in increased expenditures. Conquering the apathy among executives and the intricacy of execution are notable hurdles necessitating robust guidance and correspondence. Furthermore, attaining and upholding environmental benchmarks is critical to circumvent legal sanctions and harm to reputation. Corresponding to these findings, Mammadova et al. (2023) underscored that organizational factors exert a substantial influence on the acceptance of eco-friendly marketing approaches, impacting both internal and external facets within an organization. The internal dynamics are influenced by elements such as the environmentally conscious conduct of executives and staff, ongoing green campaigns, and the organizational readiness for change, especially in sectors like the hospitality industry. Strategic proficiencies, encompassing effective resource management and the integration of eco-conscious tactics, have been proven to enhance operational performance, notably in the hospitality sector in Indonesia (Vilkaite-Vaitone & Skackauskiene, 2020). Externally, establishing reliable, enduring partnerships with suppliers in the supply chain and fostering collaboration among providers are crucial in facilitating the assimilation of eco-friendly practices and materials, ultimately enhancing organizational effectiveness (Aseri, 2018). Additionally, the decision of management to execute Green Supply Chain Management (GSCM) is influenced by a blend of internal elements, such as existing infrastructure, and external factors, such as supplier connections (Agi, 2015).

Competitive and Business Factors are ranked fourth in terms of influencing the implementation of green marketing strategy. The study underscores the significance of competitive and business elements in influencing the implementation of green marketing strategy, encompassing clean technology development, competitiveness, consumer communication, international collaboration, future-oriented business models, and sustainable management practices. Clean technologies assume a pivotal role in green marketing by involving products and procedures that diminish environmental impacts through resource sustainability. Maintaining competitiveness is essential for

organizations to embrace green marketing strategies, serving as a mechanism to engage with environmentally conscious consumers and distinguish themselves in the marketplace. Increasing cooperation on environmental matters with other nations is imperative to tackle global challenges, while formulating future-oriented business models and prioritizing sustainable management practices are fundamental for enduring success in green marketing. The integration of environmentally sustainable practices into corporate operations is driven by the need to tackle ecological issues, enhance competitiveness, and meet the expectations of ethically conscious consumers (Mammadova et al., 2023). Enterprises that implement eco-friendly marketing strategies demonstrate a commitment to long-term sustainability, which can lead to improved customer loyalty and market positioning (Malinoshevska & Korzh, 2020). Elements such as technological progress, communication strategies, engagement with stakeholders, and financial considerations play a critical role in shaping the competitiveness of green initiatives and guiding marketing strategies towards sustainable goals (Madhushree et al., 2018).

Finally, as the results show, environmental and social factors got the last rank among the influential factors in the opinion of Iraqi managers. The significance of social and environmental awareness in influencing green marketing strategies is underscored in the study, encompassing aspects such as community awareness, heightened environmental consciousness, media coverage of environmental issues, and the increasing demand for eco-friendly products. Adapting marketing strategies in response to consumer demand for green products, driven by increased environmental consciousness, is vital for businesses. The surge in demand for sustainable products, attributed to the rise in environmental awareness influenced by media portrayal of environmental crises, presents a challenge for businesses to align with consumer preferences.

Social and environmental consciousness play a crucial role in shaping the implementation of eco-friendly marketing tactics. Scholars suggest that social capital acts as a facilitator, regulating the exchange of information among consumers, products, and marketing endeavors, thus enhancing the execution of eco-friendly marketing strategies (Setini, 2022). Additionally, understanding of environmental and social sustainability significantly impacts green trust and impulse buying behavior, especially when considering gender as a moderating factor (Khalil & Khalil, 2022). Moreover, the eco-awareness of corporate managers is positively linked to the development of innovative green products strategies, ultimately enhancing marketing performance outcomes (Yang & Liu, 2023). The increasing consumer awareness of ecological issues, coupled with the rise of environmentally conscious lifestyles, has transformed consumer preferences towards eco-friendly products, compelling firms to embrace eco-marketing strategies (Nabivi, 2020). This shift in consumer behavior highlights the importance of considering factors like pricing, availability, and product perception in influencing decisions to purchase green products, emphasizing the need for further research in this area (Agarwal, 2020).

Conclusion

The execution of green marketing strategies is influenced by a complex interplay of different factors, such as social and environmental consciousness, economic and political

circumstances, organizational capabilities, government backing, and competitive pressures. While Iraqi managers believe that environmental and social aspects have minimal influence on their decisions concerning green marketing strategies, previous studies emphasize the vital significance of prioritizing environmental sustainability and social responsibility in corporate strategies. Companies need to adapt their marketing methods to promote eco-friendly products, reduce waste and pollution, and endorse sustainable development. By doing so, they can contribute to a more sustainable future while enhancing their image and competitiveness in the market. As consumer awareness of environmental issues grows, companies must align their strategies with the preferences and needs of their customers. Nevertheless, the implementation of green marketing tactics poses challenges. Inconsistent prioritization of environmental issues by policymakers, lack of financial incentives, and public doubt can pose hurdles for businesses. Moreover, there is often a perceived conflict between environmental protection and economic progress. To address these challenges, companies should collaborate closely with policymakers, stakeholders, and non-governmental organizations to cultivate a conducive policy environment for green marketing. This may involve advocating for stricter environmental regulations, tax benefits for green investments, and public awareness initiatives. Businesses can also collaborate to establish industry benchmarks and optimal practices for green marketing.

The successful implementation of green marketing strategies hinges on various organizational, governmental, competitive, and business aspects. Organizational aspects include prioritizing green criteria in performance evaluation, investing in green technologies, and fostering a culture of sustainability. Governmental aspects encompass supportive laws and regulations, financing for green initiatives, and incentives for businesses to embrace sustainability. Competitive and business aspects involve investing in environmentally friendly technologies, interacting with socially conscious consumers, and prioritizing sustainable management practices to transition towards a more sustainable future while enhancing competitiveness and profitability. A comprehensive approach that considers social, environmental, economic, political, organizational, governmental, and competitive factors is necessary for the effective implementation of green marketing strategies. By embracing sustainability and adapting to market changes, businesses can contribute to a more sustainable future and enhance their prosperity and competitiveness.

Research limitations

The study's sample size is confined to 10 participants within the Iraq Oil and Gas Industry, potentially limiting its representativeness of the broader industry. This limitation could hinder the generalizability of the study's findings to other sectors or industries. The utilization of self-reported data from participants in the study introduces the possibility of biases and inaccuracies. Moreover, the qualitative data obtained through thematic analysis may not fully capture the intricacies of the green marketing strategies implemented by the industry. The thematic analysis method employed in the qualitative segment of the study may not be comprehensive enough to uncover all relevant themes and sub-themes. Additionally, the coding process may be susceptible to the researcher's individual biases and experiences. The findings of the study may be constrained to the specific time frame and context of the data collection. Changes in the industry landscape,

market conditions, or regulatory framework could potentially influence the efficacy of green marketing strategies over time.

References

- Aseri, A. M. (2018). Organizational factors affecting the implementation of green supply chain management. *Academy of Strategic Management Journal*, 17(5), 1-9.
- Agi, M. (2015). Analysis of the influence of organisational and inter-organisational factors on the implementation of Green Supply Chain Management practices. In 2015 International Conference on Industrial Engineering and Systems Management (IESM) (pp. 803-812). IEEE.
- Azam, W., Khan, I., & Ali, S. A. (2023). Alternative energy and natural resources in determining environmental sustainability: a look at the role of government final consumption expenditures in France. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 30(1), 1949-1965.
- Al-Waeli, A. J., Ismail, Z., & Khalid, A. A. (2020). The Impact of Environmental Costs on the Financial Performance of Industrial Companies in Iraq. *International Journal of Management (IJM)*, 11(10), 1955-1969.
- Aleksandrov, I., Daroshka, V., Trushkin, V., Chekhovskikh, I., & Ol, E. (2022). The green game: how digital technology is changing Russia's oil and gas business. In E3S Web of Conferences (Vol. 363). EDP Sciences.
- Ahmad, M., & Satrovic, E. (2023). How do fiscal policy, technological innovation, and economic openness expedite environmental sustainability?. *Gondwana Research*, 124, 143-164.
- Aastvedt, T. M., Behmiri, N. B., & Lu, L. (2021). Does green innovation damage financial performance of oil and gas companies?. *Resources Policy*, 73, 102235.
- Agarwal, V. (2020). Green buying: The impact of green marketing mix and environmental awareness on green purchase decision. *International Journal of Creative Research Thoughts (IJCRT)*, ISSN, 2320-2882.
- Aswad O.A.K., Ati E.M, Latif A.S., Ajmi R. (2023). The Future of Renewable Energy Programs in Iraq and Reality Between the Pollution Crisis and Renewable Energy Programs. *International Journal of Pharmacy Research & Technology (IJPRT)* 13(1), 60-63.
- Adamo, N., Al-Ansari, N., Sissakian, V. K., Knutsson, S., & Laue, J. (2018). Climate change: consequences on Iraq's environment. *Journal of earth sciences and geotechnical engineering*, 8(3), 43.
- Al Mashkoor, I. A. (2022). The impact of green activity-based costing and green supply chain practices on environmental performance oil refineries in Iraq. *International Journal of Economics and Finance Studies*, 14(4), 96-113.

- Al-Hersh, A. M., & Aburoub, A. S. (2015). The impact of application green marketing criteria on the marketing performance. *Global Journal of Management and Business Research*, 15(E2), 35-44.
- Amin, M. B., Shaha, S., & Bint Halim, S. Green Management System for Organizational Performances in Consumer Product Industry in Bangladesh.
- Asha, M. A. (2017). Green Marketing—An overview. *Editorial Board*, 6(4), 158.
- Al-Murad, N. Y. M. (2022). Apply Green Marketing Strategies to Improve Market Performance by Competitive Advantage as Mediating: An Analytical Study of Some Small Organizations in Iraq. *Webology*, 19(1), 1266-1281.
- Alshabebi, H. (2021). The Legal Framework of The Oil and Gas Industry In Iraq. *Akkad Journal Of Law And Public Policy*, 1(2), 44-53.
- Cheng, W., Wu, Q., Ye, F., & Li, Q. (2022). The Impact of Government Interventions and Consumer Green Preferences on the Competition between Green and Nongreen Supply Chains. *Sustainability*, 14(10), 5893.
- Alzghoul, A., Aboalghanam, K. M., & Al-Kasasbeh, O. (2024). Nexus among green marketing practice, leadership commitment, environmental consciousness, and environmental performance in Jordanian pharmaceutical sector. *Cogent Business & Management*, 11(1), 2292308.
- Bratanegara, A. S., Somantri, L., Astari, A. J., Ihsan, M. H., & Aliyan, S. A. (2022). The important of environmental awareness and industrial hygiene for workers. In *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science* (Vol. 1089, No. 1, p. 012073). IOP Publishing.
- Ben-Naceur, K. (2019). How the oil and gas industry is contributing to sustainability. *Journal of Petroleum Technology*, 71(03), 38-39.
- Barforoush, N., Etebarian, A., Naghsh, A., & Shahin, A. (2021). Green innovation a strategic resource to attain competitive advantage. *International Journal of Innovation Science*, 13(5), 645-663.
- Bond, S., Diprose, G., & Thomas, A. C. (2018). Seeking Climate Justice. *Findings Report on Oil Free Activism and Oil and Gas Development*, 2013-2016.
- Chen J., Li Q., Wang X., (2022). Does the government's environmental attention improve enterprise green innovation?—Evidence from china, *Environmental Economics and Management*, Volume 10 - 2022
| <https://doi.org/10.3389/fenvs.2022.999492>.
- Cismaş, L. M., Boţoteanu, G. I., Cojocaru, T. M., & Gruescu, R. M. (2023). Significance of corporate non-financial information disclosure for sustainable economic growth. *J. Green Econ. Low-Carbon Dev*, 2(1), 1-10.

- Cohen, M. A., Cui, S., & Gao, F. (2019). The effect of government support on green product design and environmental impact. Available at SSRN 3291017.
- Cheng, X., Chen, K., & Su, Y. (2023). Green innovation in oil and gas exploration and production for meeting the sustainability goals. *Resources Policy*, 87, 104315.
- Chauhan, S., & Naznin, N. (2023). Green Marketing: An Ethical and Anti-Environmental Resilient Approach for Sustainable Business. *Problemy Ekorozwoju*, 18(2), 141-147.
- Dementieva, A. G., & Sokolova, M. I. (2022). Ecological Vector of Social Responsibility in Energy Companies. In *Industry 4.0: Fighting Climate Change in the Economy of the Future* (pp. 255-267). Cham: Springer International Publishing.
- Duttgupta, A., Islam, M., Hosseinabad, E. R., & Zaman, M. A. U. (2021). Corporate social responsibility and sustainability: a perspective from the oil and gas industry. *Journal of Nature, Science & Technology*, 2, 22-29.
- Esmaelnezhad, D., Lagzi, M. D., Antucheviciene, J., Hashemi, S. S., & Khorshidi, S. (2023). Evaluation of green marketing strategies by considering sustainability criteria. *Sustainability*, 15(10), 7874.
- Elsaman, H. A., & Sergio, R. P. (2021). the psychographics of green marketing strategy vis-a-vis corporate social responsibility: Implications to organisational growth. *International Journal of Entrepreneurship*, 25, 1-11.
- Faraz, N. A., Ahmed, F., & Xiong, Z. (2024). How firms leverage corporate environmental strategy to nurture green behavior: Role of multi-level environmentally responsible leadership. *Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management*, 31(1), 243-259.
- Fenglan, L. (2010). An analysis of the dynamic game model between government and enterprises of green supply chain. In 2010 International Conference on Management and Service Science.
- Firdiansyah, R., Mohamed, M., Yusoff Yusliza, M., Saputra, J., & Muhammad, Z. (2021). A Review of green marketing strategy literature: Mini review approach. In *Proceedings of the 11th Annual International Conference on Industrial Engineering and Operations Management Singapore: IEOM Society International*, Vol. 21030, pp. 5092-5108.
- Guba, E. G., & Lincoln, Y. S. (1994). Competing paradigms in qualitative research. *Handbook of qualitative research*, 2(163-194), 105.
- Guo, M., Nowakowska-Grunt, J., Gorbanyov, V., & Egorova, M. (2020). Green technology and sustainable development: Assessment and green growth frameworks. *Sustainability*, 12(16), 6571.

- Garg, A., Dhaliwal, R. S., & Gupta, S. (2021). Prioritizing factors determining environmental responsibility using fuzzy analytical hierarchy process: evidence from India. *International Journal of Social Economics*, 48(7), 999-1020.
- Gupta, M., & Dharwal, M. (2022). Green entrepreneurship and sustainable development: A conceptual framework. *Materials Today: Proceedings*, 49, 3603-3606.
- Heim, I., Vigneau, A. C., & Kalyuzhnova, Y. (2023). Environmental and socio-economic policies in oil and gas regions: triple bottom line approach. *Regional Studies*, 57(1), 181-195.
- Ibrahim, M. D., & Alola, A. A. (2020). Integrated analysis of energy-economic development-environmental sustainability nexus: Case study of MENA countries. *Science of the Total Environment*, 737, 139768.
- Javeed, S. A., Teh, B. H., Ong, T. S., Chong, L. L., Abd Rahim, M. F. B., & Latief, R. (2022). How does green innovation strategy influence corporate financing? Corporate social responsibility and gender diversity play a moderating role. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 19(14), 8724.
- Jianling Xu, Jiao Hong & Zhiyuan Zhou (2023) Local Attention to Environment and Green Innovation: Evidence from Listed Manufacturing Companies in 120 Cities in China, *Emerging Markets Finance and Trade*, 59:4, 1062-1073, DOI: 10.1080/1540496X.2022.2128753
- Johnston, J., & Cushing, L. (2020). Chemical exposures, health, and environmental justice in communities living on the fenceline of industry. *Current environmental health reports*, 7, 48-57.
- Khalil, M. K., & Khalil, R. (2022). Leveraging buyers' interest in ESG investments through sustainability awareness. *Sustainability*, 14(21), 14278.
- Kadhim, H. A., Abd, W. H., & Kareem, A. D. (2020). The impact of environmental auditing on the environmental dimension of sustainable development (Applied Research on" Environmental Governmental Institutions in Iraq). *Ilkogretim Online*, 19(3), 2801-2812.
- Kaupke, K., & zu Knyphausen-Aufseß, D. (2023). Sustainability and firm value in the oil and gas industry—A vicious circle?. *Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management*, 30(3), 1129-1144.
- Koshesh, O. S., & Jafari, H. R. (2019). The environmental strategic analysis of oil & gas industries in the Kurdistan Region using PESTLE, SWOT and FDEMATEL. *Pollution*, 5(3), 537-554.
- Khan, A. J., Shah, S. Z. A., Bashir, F., & Iqbal, J. (2021). Antecedents and Consequences of Green Human Resource Management in Oil and Gas Companies

- of Pakistan. *Sustainable Business and Society in Emerging Economies*, 3(3), 339-351.
- Kotler, P., Berger, R., & Bickhoff, N. (2010). The quintessence of strategic management. What You Really Need to Know to Survive in Business, Berlin.
- López-Torres, J. F., Sánchez-García, J. Y., Núñez-Ríos, J. E., & López-Hernández, C. (2023). Prioritizing factors for effective strategy implementation in small and medium-size organizations. *European Business Review*, 35(5), 694-712.
- Lin, M., & Lin, Y. (2023). Government Incentive and R&D Innovation: Based on the Research of Environmental Protection Listed Companies. *Frontiers in Business, Economics and Management*, 9(1), 244-247.
- Lai, K. H., Feng, Y., & Zhu, Q. (2023). Digital transformation for green supply chain innovation in manufacturing operations. *Transportation Research Part E: Logistics and Transportation Review*, 175, 103145.
- Mukonza, C., & Swarts, I. (2020). The influence of green marketing strategies on business performance and corporate image in the retail sector. *Business strategy and the Environment*, 29(3), 838-845.
- Marsiglio, S., Privileggi, F. (2021). On the economic growth and environmental trade-off: a multi-objective analysis. *Ann Oper Res* 296, 263–289.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10479-019-03217-y>
- Manunggal, W. T. K. (2022). Green marketing for eco-friendly vegetable products at Wanita Tani Karya Manunggal Group. *Jurnal Pengabdian Masyarakat Universitas Merdeka Malang*, 7(4), 814-823.
- Madhushree, L. M., Revathi, R., & PS, A. (2018). Competitive Strategies in Green Business-A Case Study on Aegis Logistics Ltd. *International Journal of Case Studies in Business, IT and Education (IJCSBE)*, 2-6.
- Moyel, M. S., Fawzi, N. A. M., Mehdi, B. A., Hassan, W. F., & Sabty, M. (2023). Assessment of Community Awareness and Knowledge of Environmental Law and Legislation in the Basrah Governorate (Iraq). *Planning*, 18(8), 2387-2392.
- Malinoshevska, K., & Korzh, M. (2020). Marketing Strategies Of Development On The Example Of Green Tourism. *Three Seas Economic Journal*, 1(2), 25-34.
- Mammadova, V. Q., Hasanov, A. F., & Hasanova, A. A. (2023). Green marketing and factors affecting its development. In *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science* (Vol. 1206, No. 1, p. 012006). IOP Publishing.
- Mashkoo, I. A. A., Ali, J. H., & Al-Kanani, M. M. (2023). The Role of Green Activity-Based Costing in Achieving Sustainability Development: Evidence From Iraq. *International Journal of Professional Business Review*, 8(4), e01276-e01276.

- Mammadova, V. Q., Hasanov, A. F., & Hasanova, A. A. (2023, June). Green marketing and factors affecting its development. In IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science (Vol. 1206, No. 1, p. 012006). IOP Publishing.
- Morrow, R., Rodriguez, A., & King, N. (2015). Colaizzi's descriptive phenomenological method. *The psychologist*, 28(8), 643-644.
- Motilewa, D. B., Ibidunni, A. S., Worlu, R., Moses, C. L., Obi, J., & Dirisu, J. (2019). Influence of ecological protection on the corporate image of oil and gas firms in Nigeria. *Business: Theory and Practice*, 20, 19-24.
- Mojarad, A. A. S., Atashbari, V., & Tantau, A. (2018). Challenges for sustainable development strategies in oil and gas industries. In Proceedings of the International Conference on Business Excellence (Vol. 12, No. 1, pp. 626-638).
- Mansour, W., Maseeh, A. N., Celiku, B., Laure, A. H., Haddad, M., & Lu, Z. C. (2020). Iraq Economic Monitor: Navigating the Perfect Storm (Redux).
- Mäkitie T., Normann H.E., Thune T.M., Gonzalez J.S. (2019). The green flings: norwegian oil and gas industry's engagement in offshore wind power, *energy Policy*, 127, pp. 269-279.
- Nabivi, E. (2020). Implementation of green marketing concept through social media activities: A systematic literature review. *Journal of Marketing and Consumer Behaviour in Emerging Markets*, 11(2), 55-67.
- Ottman, J. A., Stafford, E. R., & Hartman, C. L. (2006). Avoiding green marketing myopia: Ways to improve consumer appeal for environmentally preferable products. *Environment: science and policy for sustainable development*, 48(5), 22-36.
- Obeidat, S. M., Al Bakri, A. A., & Elbanna, S. (2020). Leveraging "green" human resource practices to enable environmental and organizational performance: Evidence from the Qatari oil and gas industry. *Journal of business ethics*, 164, 371-388.
- Oluwasanmi, O. O., & Ogunro, V. O. (2018). Green marketing, green consumerism, and environmental sustainability in the Nigerian petroleum industry: An overview. Joseph Ayo Babalola University *International Journal of Social and Management Sciences*, 6(1), 228-242.
- Peattie, K. (2016). *Green marketing*. In *The marketing book* (pp. 573-597). Routledge.
- Pacevičiūtė, A., & Razbadauskaitė-Venskė, I. (2023). The role of green marketing in creating a sustainable competitive advantage. Regional formation and development studies: *journal of social sciences.*, (2), 89-98.
- Panait, M., Ionescu, R., Gigauri, I., & Palazzo, M. (2021, December). Maintaining Green Goals in Disruptive Times: Evidences from the European Energy Sector.

- In International Conference on Economic Scientific Research-Theoretical, *Empirical and Practical Approaches* (pp. 145-155). Cham: Springer International Publishing.
- Rizvi, Y. S., & Garg, R. (2021). The simultaneous effect of green ability-motivation-opportunity and transformational leadership in environment management: the mediating role of green culture. *Benchmarking: An International Journal*, 28(3), 830-856.
- Resen, E. J., & AbdulRazzaq, M. S. (2022). An Evaluation of Environmental Performance According to The International Standard (ISO14001: 2015) in a Field East of Baghdad/A Case Study in the Midline Oil Company. *Journal of Economics and Administrative Sciences*, 28(134), 29-56.
- Rademaker, C. A., & Royne, M. B. (2018). Thinking green: How marketing managers select media for consumer acceptance. *Journal of Business Strategy*, 39(2), 30-38.
- Shittu, O., & Nygaard, C. (2021). Green marketing and social practices: Managing people as carriers of sustainability practices. *Green Marketing and Management in Emerging Markets: The Crucial Role of People Management in Successful Implementation*, 45-57.
- Saraiva, I. (2022). The Contribution of Green Marketing to Brand Strengthening and Consumer Loyalty: The LUSH Case. In *Advances in Design and Digital Communication II: Proceedings of the 5th International Conference on Design and Digital Communication, Digicom 2021, November 4–6, 2021, Barcelos, Portugal* (pp. 631-638). Springer International Publishing.
- Setini, M. (2022). CAN GREEN MARKETING BE ACHIEVED? DRIVEN BY SOCIAL CAPITAL TOWARDS PRODUCT INNOVATION AND CUSTOMER ORIENTATION. *Jurnal Ilmiah Manajemen dan Bisnis*, 7(2), 195-204.
- Sasu, C., Saadia, K. H., & Abdelmadjid, K. (2017). The role of environmental responsibility in the adoption of green marketing: The case of petroleum companies in Arab countries. *International Journal for Innovation Education and Research*, 5(11), 103-139.
- Saeed I. M., Tarkhany A., Hama Y., & Al-Shatri Sh. (2023). Environmental considerations, sustainability opportunities and Iraqi government's energy policies: a comparative study, *Environment, Development and Sustainability: A Multidisciplinary Approach to the Theory and Practice of Sustainable Development*, Springer, vol. 25(7), pages 6879-6895, July.
- Shah, S. Q. A., Lai, F. W., Shad, M. K., & Jan, A. A. (2022). Developing a green governance framework for the performance enhancement of the oil and gas industry. *Sustainability*, 14(7), 3735.
- Taghavi, E., Fallahpour, A., Wong, K. Y., & Hoseini, S. A. (2021). Identifying and prioritizing the effective factors in the implementation of green supply chain

management in the construction industry. *Sustainable Operations and Computers*, 2, 97-106.

- Tuni, A., Rentizelas, A., & Chinese, D. (2020). An integrative approach to assess environmental and economic sustainability in multi-tier supply chains. *Production Planning & Control*, 31(11-12), 861-882.
- Tillotson, P., Slade, R., Staffell, I., & Halttunen, K. (2023). Deactivating climate activism? The seven strategies oil and gas majors use to counter rising shareholder action. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 103, 103190.
- Umar, S., & Wei, Q. (2022). Improving the Efficiency of Firm's Environmental Strategy Through Environmentally Oriented Corporate. In *Academy of Management Proceedings*, 1(2022), 11217. Briarcliff Manor, NY 10510: Academy of Management.
- Vilkaite-Vaitone, N., & Skackauskiene, I. (2020). Factors affecting implementation of green marketing orientation. In *SHS Web of Conferences* (Vol. 74, p. 01036). EDP Sciences.
- Vihristyuk, O., & Dimitrova, A. (2022, October). The Study of Social Risks Affecting the Financial Stability of the Oil and Gas Industry and The Ways of Enterprise Management. In *2022 V International Conference on High Technology for Sustainable Development (HiTech)* (pp. 1-5). IEEE.
- Vevere, V., & Shina, I. (2023, June). The Factors of Green Marketing Affecting Consumer Purchase Intention in Latvia. In *ENVIRONMENT. TECHNOLOGIES. RESOURCES. Proceedings of the International Scientific and Practical Conference* (Vol. 1, pp. 240-246).
- Vardhan, A., Ehtesham, H., & Gani, A. (2022, August). Identification, ranking, and prioritization of factors impacting green product design using the fuzzy AHP approach. In *Biennial International Conference on Future Learning Aspects of Mechanical Engineering* (pp. 285-295). Singapore: Springer Nature Singapore.
- Vilkaite-Vaitone, N., & Skackauskiene, I. (2020). Factors affecting implementation of green marketing orientation. In *SHS Web of Conferences*, (74). Sciences.
- Wang, L., & Pan, F. (2023). Incentive Mechanism Analysis of Environmental Governance Using Multitask Principal-Agent Model. *Sustainability*, 15(5), 4126.
- Wang, B., Han, S., Ao, Y., Liao, F., Wang, T., & Chen, Y. (2022). The impact of public opinion pressure on construction company green innovations: the mediating effect of leaders' environmental intention and the moderating effect of environmental regulation. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13, 936058.
- Widyastuti, S., Said, M., Siswono, S., & Firmansyah, D. A. (2019). *Customer trust through green corporate image, green marketing strategy, and social responsibility: A case study*.

- Wymer, W., & Polonsky, M. J. (2015). The limitations and potentialities of green marketing. *Journal of Nonprofit & Public Sector Marketing*, 27(3), 239-262.
- Yang, G., & Liu, B. (2023). Retracted Article: Research on the impact of managers' green environmental awareness and strategic intelligence on corporate green product innovation strategic performance. *Annals of Operations Research*, 326(Suppl 1), 5-5.
- Zheng, Q., Li, J., & Duan, X. (2023). The Impact of Environmental Tax and R&D Tax Incentives on Green Innovation. *Sustainability*, 15(9), 7303.
- Zhao, Y., Mao, J., & Li, Y. (2022). Local governments' environmental emphasis and corporate green innovation: evidence from China. *Economic Change and Restructuring*, 55(4), 2577-2603.

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